

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 12/01/2026

Accepted: 17/02/2026

Published: 28/02/2026

Citation: Prajapati R, Joshi H (2026) Regression Tree-based Ensemble Method for Short-Term Cloud Workload Prediction on Nonlinear Time Series Data. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(8): 481-497. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i8.44>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Regression Tree-based Ensemble Method for Short-Term Cloud Workload Prediction on Nonlinear Time Series Data

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Abstract

Objectives: This work focuses on accurate and precise short-term cloud workload estimation on nonlinear and dynamic workloads to achieve non-disruptive resource management, scalability, and a cost-effective environment. **Methods:** The suggested method provides an individual training and testing model for capturing the dataset pattern and validating future estimations. The training model is implemented with an optimized parameter contribution rate that replaces the learning rate hyperparameter of the boosting method (XGBoost), whereas the testing model is designed by performing statistical operations on the residuals of the individually trained models and optimized window size. To assess the strength and performance, the approach is compared with the results of baseline methods. **Findings:** To evaluate the accuracy and reliability, performance metrics were evaluated by training the suggested technique and baseline methods on 80% of the dataset to observe the nonlinear behavior, and testing on the remaining 20% of the GWA-BITBRAIN cloud workload. In the experimental results of the training phase, the suggested technique outperformed and showed a significant reduction of 84%, 81%, 76%, 74%, 70%, and 30% in RMSE compared to all baseline methods, respectively. Similarly, the proposed method enhanced the model accuracy with the lowest MAE. This lower model error demonstrates the ability of the model to capture the complex nonlinear relationships in the dataset. During the testing phase, the proposed methods observed 62%, 61%, 27%, 41%, 22%, and 16% less estimation RMSE than baseline methods, respectively, which reveals higher reductions in errors, showing accurate CPU usage predictions. This accurate estimation reveals the reliability and robustness of the model in short-term workload estimation. This method also proved its fitness with 6% reductions in model RMSE error than earlier presented work. **Novelty:** The contribution rate highly influences the prediction of each weak learner, following the percentage of residuals during each iteration. Testing model statistical operations focus on possible future values from the optimized window.

Keywords: Regression Tree; Resource Estimation; Ensemble method XGBoost; Cloud Workload; Non-Linear Time Series Data

1 Introduction

As the cloud infrastructure is purely dynamic and resources are highly fluctuating in demand, resource estimation is essential for offering an uninterrupted and QoS (Quality of Service) based cloud environment. Many machine learning models are implemented for short-term and long-term cloud resource predictions. In the proposed work, short-term resource utilization is predicted, which is highly probable to be more accurate than long-term predictions.

Cloud resources utilization data are time series data⁽¹⁾. Time series data are of two types: univariate and multivariate. Time series data is a long sequence of data experiencing a linear or nonlinear trend. Linear data is either increasing or decreasing, whereas nonlinear data shows a mixture of up and down trends, regularly or irregularly. Since time series data are continuous, the data falls into a regression problem. Therefore, statistical models, machine learning, and deep learning-based regression techniques are well suited for regression analysis. Time series data exhibit the sequence of data with an internal relationship. Hence, deep learning-based models such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), which employ multiple layers as neurons to understand the complex patterns from data⁽²⁾.

Accurate cloud load prediction is a promising task and ongoing research work. Recently, many machine learning models have been implemented for the prediction of cloud resources. They used the ARIMA, SARIMA, and LSTM models for estimating the net profit in business⁽³⁾. The author forecasted the food demand supply chain by applying bagging, boosting, and deep learning-based techniques⁽⁴⁾. They evaluated the models LR, BPNN, and XGBoost on data from each month for future predictions of electric power to avoid unavailability⁽⁵⁾. The author divided the nonlinear dataset into multiple linear sections, and an AR model was fitted on each for prediction of the next range of data for software aging performance⁽⁶⁾. They developed a hybrid model of Recurrent Neural Networks implemented on BitBrains' distributed DC dataset, which includes performance metrics for 1,750 virtual machines for estimating future cloud usage⁽⁷⁾. They performed a comparative analysis of the Hybrid model ARIMA-NARNET (ARIMA-Nonlinear Autoregressive Neural Network), a combination of ARIMA and neural networks, experimented with for coconut price prediction on a nonlinear dataset⁽⁸⁾. For better prediction, they proposed an Ensemble Forecasting Approach (EFA) that comprised Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD) and R-Transformer⁽⁹⁾. They explored feature selection and error correction methods to improve the prediction accuracy of LightGBM and XGBoost on historical load⁽¹⁰⁾. Due to nonlinear behavior, a single model is not capable of capturing the irregular patterns for future predictions, which require multiple models comprised of several weak learners to gradually reduce the errors for accurate future predictions. As the ensemble technique enhances the learning process, the author proposed such an ensemble method with an amalgamation of Workload Prediction Methods and an Adaptive Model Selector on 80% of the Alibaba Data Set, BitBrains Data Set, and Google Dataset⁽¹¹⁾.

They experimented with a three-way decision-based ensemble (TWD-RCPM) method composed of three different prediction methods, i.e., Exponential Moving Average for stable data, Holt-Winter for jitter period holding data, and a weighted method for volatility period holding data⁽¹²⁾. Three different RNN models, i.e., LSTM, GRU, and MGU, were implemented with the weak learner as a decision tree. The suggested ensemble framework is evaluated on four different types of datasets, and RMSE is used as the performance metric. XGBoost is evaluated with an exact greedy algorithm, an approximate algorithm, and a weighted quantile sketch for the best solution for tree splitting for quick tree learning⁽¹³⁾. To estimate the cloud workload, smooth wavelet transformation and contrastive learning using deep learning models are evaluated on different cloud workload datasets⁽¹⁴⁾.

The author used the TSFRESH open-source library for the selection of statistical and time series features such as variance, standard deviation, and many more for each selected lag model to improve prediction accuracy⁽¹¹⁾. A tree-splitting-based method for input space division was proposed for increasing the homogeneity (purity) of the samples at the terminal node based on the value of the hyperparameter (λ). To evaluate the performance, the suggested technique was compared with other standard methods (Entropy, Gain Ratio, Gini Index, Tsallis Entropy, Tsallis GR) on 17 different datasets⁽¹⁵⁾.

For short-term forecasting, each subset of six datasets is trained individually by three machine learning and three deep learning models. To derive the optimized models and predictor variables, trained models are evaluated on the validation dataset. These obtained variables are used to train the ensemble learning models. Moreover, the test dataset is used by the optimized trained models for achieving the predictor variables. These variables are further processed by ensemble learning models to estimate the final predictions⁽¹⁶⁾.

Due to nonlinear data, a single model as a prediction estimator cannot learn complex relationships, resulting in poor performance. In response to this issue, ensemble techniques are preferable, as they gradually increase the accuracy of machine learning models by involving many weak learners, i.e., decision trees or regression trees, depending on the classification or regression problem. Bagging and boosting are two techniques of ensemble learning⁽¹⁷⁾. Bagging trains multiple weak learners that learn from each other concurrently and produces a strong learner by averaging all models. Boosting builds the models

sequentially, with each subsequent model minimizing the errors of the previous one to produce a strong model with high accuracy.

Here, the targeted dataset is a nonlinear cloud workload where the trend of the data switches predictably or unpredictably over the long interval. Hence, the ensemble boosting technique is more suitable, as it sequentially improves the fitness of the model by capturing the right patterns of data. In machine learning, tree structure-based boosting models can predict nonlinear data accurately, as the data is split into decision rules⁽¹⁵⁾. Some tree-based boosting techniques, like Gradient Boosting Regressor (GB), Extreme Gradient Boosting Regressor (XGB), and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM), are more appropriate for short-term to long-term predictions.

Earlier, research scholars have explored various hybrid models that combine different machine learning and deep learning techniques in the expectation of estimating an effective model for nonlinear patterns. The motivation behind this is to improve the overall accuracy of the estimator by employing the models as needed.

Ensemble boosting technique XGBoost selects the best tree split to define the decision rules and calculates the leaf score. This model adds equal portions (learning rate) of the leaf score to the outcome of the previous weak learner for the prediction of new data. However, this is irrespective of the weightage of the residuals, indicating how many percentages of the predicted data are far from the actual data. This mechanism results in slow learning and convergence with many iterations. This requires a proper technique for considering the right amount of leaf score used by each weak learner to add to the outcome of the previous weak learner for generating the next strong weak learner.

However, any existing boosting model that is not customized with optimized hyperparameters does not help the model learn quickly with higher accuracy and fast convergence.

Hence, to address this issue, we approached a regression tree structure-based ensemble technique that developed training and testing models separately for quick convergence and accurate prediction. The training model is designed with a new hyperparameter contribution rate, which replaced the existing parameter learning rate and benefits some present features of the XGBoost method. This contribution rate reveals the percentage of residuals for each data point during each iteration with respect to the outcome of the first model. This approach adds a variable proportion of leaf score to the outcome of the previous weak learner, whereas the learning rate adds an equal proportion to each weak learner's outcome based on a set fixed value to produce the next strong weak learner. This new mechanism helps the model to converge quickly, resulting in learning the underlying nonlinear pattern early with fewer iterations and stable performance. This effective training model facilitates a reliable testing model, which enhances the prediction accuracy on unseen data.

Here, the approached model focuses on short-term workload predictions for the good fitness of models rather than long-term predictions. In this work, we mainly focus on the CPU resource utilization of cloud data centers for workload predictions; hence, we conducted univariate time series data analysis.

The paper is organized as follows: In section 2 the proposed methodology and motivation are explained. In section 3, Experimental results and discussion are presented. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusion of the work carried out and future work.

2 Methodology

Cloud resources are highly fluctuating in demand, which results in the nonlinear data holding regular or irregular patterns repeatedly. In this prediction, we use statistical time series forecasting models and machine learning models for future predictions on nonlinear time series data.

2.1 Dataset Description

To assess the strength of the approach model, cloud workload tracing data was obtained from Gwa-Bitbrains cloud data center. This dataset holds the cloud workload traces from 1,750 VMs operating in a production-level cloud infrastructure from GWA-Bitbrains, a cloud service provider that delivers various hosting and management services for banking, insurance, and other business applications. Traced data for 1,250 virtual machines (VMs) over a month is stored in FastStorage connected to fast storage area network (SAN) storage devices, while traced data for 500 VMs over the months of July, August, and September 2013 is stored in Rnd, connected to either SAN devices or much slower NAS (Network Attached Storage) devices. To identify the functional behavior of VMs and the accurate modeling of nonlinear cloud workload, workload data from 121 VMs at an interval of 5 milliseconds in the months of August and September 2013 was utilized from the Rnd trace. This huge workload metric ensures consistency and compatibility with standard cloud workload specifications and restricts the loss of useful information and cloud workload patterns. With a comprehensive and heterogeneous dataset behavior, the model effectively identifies the underlying cloud workload patterns and estimates robust future resource predictions. The cloud infrastructure

consumes heterogeneous resources, but cloud server utilization is directly proportional to CPU usage⁽⁹⁾. Hence, the attributes CPU capacity provisioned (Megahertz), CPU usage (Megahertz), and timestamp from 10 features of the dataset are considered for workload prediction⁽¹⁸⁾. Each VM CPU core (Single core, Dual core, and Octa core CPU) is provisioned with a different capacity, i.e., 2600, 2700, 2926, 4800, 5200, 11704, and 23407 in MHz.

2.2 Dataset Preprocessing

Data preparation is an essential part of data analysis and machine learning. Compatibility is ensured, model complexity is decreased, model accuracy is increased, and data quality is enhanced⁽¹⁹⁾. Data transformation and cleansing are two of the many steps in the process, and they are completed below.

2.2.1. Data Cleaning

Data cleaning is basically the process of transforming raw data into a form that is accurate, consistent, and ready for analysis. Such processes improve reliability, efficiency, and model performance. They stated that missing data, noisy data, and outliers are then addressed by this process⁽¹⁹⁾.

2.2.1.1. Handling Missing Data. Before confirming the completion of the dataset, missing values were examined for completeness and reliability. The examination was performed to identify any null or zero values that could affect model performance. It was observed that the features "cpu capacity provisioned" and "cpu usage" were holding less than 10% of their total entries with zero values. Hence, these features were filled with mean imputation⁽²⁰⁾. As regards imputation, all features were examined for distribution and resulted in an asymmetric distribution with positive skewness.

2.2.2. Data Transformation

Data transformation helps to provide uniformity across the dataset (between 0 and 1) and reduces the impact of outliers and skewness. Compatible data makes the characteristics easier to interpret and improves model performance. From the available features, CPU capacity provisioned and CPU usage, CPU usage percentage is calculated.

2.2.3. Motivation

The model can easily learn and estimate from the linear or seasonal trend, but nonlinear data can lead the single model to fail to estimate accurately. The ensemble boosting method proved its strength in the estimation of nonlinear data. In machine learning, many variants of the ensemble boosting technique are well known, i.e., AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, LightGBM, XGBoost, and many more. Hence, in this paper, a regression tree structure-based ensemble technique is proposed.

2.2.4. Proposed Architecture

A tree structure-based boosting architecture is well-suited for non-linear data due to its splitting of decision rules. Cloud workloads exhibit nonlinear data patterns, so this work presents a technique that benefits from the features of the XGBoost model, and new mathematical concepts are added for cloud load predictions that help improve the model's efficiency and accuracy. This technique is developed for both the training phase and the testing phase, as described below. The proposed architecture depicted in Figure 1 works as follows:

2.2.4.1. Training Phase. This phase is designed to train the model to learn the behaviour from the underlying dataset for future prediction that is illustrated in Figure 1. In this process, cloud workload is split into five buckets and each individually trained by multiple weak learners sequentially to minimize the residuals, where each weak learner is regression tree. Tree base ensemble models effectively recognize and decipher patterns from small ranges grouped into bucket.

Model trained on each bucket well focus on same range of values in historical data for future prediction. Bucketing also helps in minimizing the effect of noise and outliers during training. Ensemble techniques support the regularization to avoid the overfitting caused by bucketing. The working for one of the weak learner is shown in Figure 2. This technique helps the model in capturing the pattern of the data and improves fitness of model. Working of suggested model represented as below:

Step 1

For evaluating performance of the model, cloud workload dataset divided into 80% training and 20% testing ratio. For increasing the fitness of the model, training dataset divided in five buckets. The mathematical explanation for bucketing is described below,

$X = \{ x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \}$, where X is a continuous variable for cpu_usage_percentage holding continuous data.

Step 1: Define a minimum and maximum for the range of each bucket

$$x_{\min} = \text{minimum}(X), x_{\max} = \text{maximum}(X)$$

Step 2: Define the range for a value of the bucket

$$w = \frac{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}{k}$$

Step 3: Define Bucket Boundaries

$$B_j = [x_{\min} + jw, (j + 1)w], \text{ where } j=0,1,2,3,4,5,\dots, k, \text{ where } k \text{ is a number of buckets.}$$

In this dataset $x_{\min} = 1.002$ and $x_{\max} = 99.89$, so $w=99.89-1/5=20$, (approximately) range for each bucket. So buckets 1 to 20, 21 to 40, 41 to 60, 61 to 80 and 81 to 100 will be created as per step 3. The suggested model evaluated on each bucket separately and illustrated the procedure for individual weak learner on one of the bucket as below.

In this model, $F = \{f_0(x), f_1(x), \dots, f_n(x)\}$ are set of base learners. Prediction of each model described as

$$\widehat{Y}_t = \sum_{t=1, i=1}^n f_t(x_i)$$

Where $t = 1, 2, \dots, n$ no. of weak learners and $i=1, 2, \dots, n$ data points. As the first predictor, model initialize with constant value

$$f_0(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n l(Y_i, \widehat{Y}) \tag{1}$$

Sequentially each weak learner fits on the residuals calculated as,

$$r_{it} = - \left[\frac{\partial l(Y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial (F(x_i))} \right] \tag{2}$$

where $F(x) = F_{t-1}^{(x)}$ for $t, i=1, 2, \dots, n$ and $l(Y_i, F(x_i))$ is the loss function. Contribution rate i.e. percentage of the residuals w.r.t mean of actual data ($f_0(x)$) defined as

$$pr_{it} = - \left[\frac{r_{it} * 100}{f_0(x)} \right] \tag{3}$$

This parameter behaves as a hyperparameter learning rate in the boosting model, which determines how quickly the model converges to the optimal solution by minimizing the loss function during optimization. A learning rate that is too low leads the model to converge slowly, while one that is too high causes the model to overfit. The learning rate is used as a constant prefix value, making the same amount of changes to each data prediction, which leads to the model training slowly. Consequently, all high or low errors (residuals) are treated with the same learning rate. Eventually, selecting the ideal learning rate requires optimization and a promising task that converges the model to an optimal solution. This suggested contribution rate reveals the percentage of the gap between actual data and predicted data for each data point. This approach contributes to the prediction corresponding to the proportion of error held by each data point. Hence, the contribution rate overcomes the learning rate in achieving the optimal solution quickly.

STEP 2

The objective function is described as,

$$L^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n l(Y_i, \widehat{Y}_{t-1} + f_t(x_i)) \tag{4}$$

Newton-Raphson method to approximate the root of the loss function. However, Newton-Raphson finds the best root approximation at the second derivative. So by expanding (1) with Tayloros approximation series up to the second derivative as

$$f(a+x) = f(a) + x f'(a) + \frac{1}{2} x^2 f''(a) \tag{5}$$

By putting the (5) in (4)

$$L^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[l(Y_i, \widehat{Y}_{t-1}) + f_t(x_i) g_i + \frac{1}{2} f_t^2(x_i) h_i + \Omega(f_t) \right] \tag{6}$$

Where $g_i = \partial_{\widehat{y}_{t-1}} l(Y_i, \widehat{Y}_{t-1})$ and $h_i = \partial^2_{\widehat{y}_{t-1}} (Y_i, \widehat{Y}_{t-1})$ and replacing Ω with the regularization term, (6) can be written as below.

$$L^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[f_t(x_i) g_i + \frac{1}{2} f_t^2(x_i) h_i + \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^T w_j^2 \right] \tag{7}$$

$f_t(x_i)$ be the regression tree added iteratively. γ be the regularization term which penalizes the T (number of leaves in tree) and penalizes weights (w_j) of the leaves. This way, managing the number of leaves with reasonable weight prevents the model from being overfit.

If I_j is considered as the instance set in leaf j, by replacing the complete tree with the leaves' weight, (7) can be written as.

$$L^{(t)} = \sum_{j=1}^T \left[\left(\sum_{i \in I_j} g_i \right) w_j + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i \in I_j} h_i + \right) w_j^2 + \gamma T \right] \tag{8}$$

By considering (5) equal to zero

$$w_j = - \frac{\sum_{i \in I_j} g_i}{\sum_{i \in I_j} h_i + T} \tag{9}$$

The above equation can be expanded into the following form

$$w_j = \frac{g_1 + g_2 + g_3 + \dots + g_n}{h_1 + h_2 + h_3 + \dots + h_n + T} \tag{10}$$

For regression, if the loss function is $\frac{1}{2}(Y_i - \widehat{Y}_i)$ for i^{th} the data point, then the first derivative (g) is $-(Y_i - \widehat{Y}_i)$ and the second derivative (h) is 1. Hence, equation (10) for n numbers of data points can be written as

$$w_j = - \frac{-(Y_1 - \widehat{Y}_1) + -(Y_2 - \widehat{Y}_2) + \dots - (Y_n - \widehat{Y}_n)}{h_1 + h_2 + h_3 + \dots + h_n + T} \tag{11}$$

$$w_j = \frac{(Y_1 - \widehat{Y}_1) + (Y_2 - \widehat{Y}_2) + \dots + (Y_n - \widehat{Y}_n)}{h_1 + h_2 + h_3 + \dots + h_n + T} \tag{12}$$

$$w_j = \frac{\text{sum of residuals}}{\text{no. of residuals} + T} \tag{13}$$

The above can be used to calculate the leaf weight or leaf score after the tree-splitting method. Leaf score determines the prediction value for each leaf node in the tree. During future predictions, the leaf score from the tree leaf node in which the data point falls is added to the model's current prediction.

STEP 3

Many decision tree stumps are created based on pr_{it} for each data point. The best tree split selected with a low weighted average variance, as low weighted average variance indicates low variability for continuous data. When a node gets split, the resulting left and child nodes have different size of data points. Weighted average variance weights to proportion of child nodes, confirms that larger node has more influence on the quality of tree split measure while normal variance gives equal weightage to small and large nodes. Consider that the tree is split from V data points with two leaf nodes V_L and V_R . Now consider that the variance for left and right child nodes are σ^2_L and σ^2_R . The weighted average variance for each tree stump is calculated as,

$$\sigma^2_w = \left(\frac{V_L}{V} \right) \sigma^2_L + \left(\frac{V_R}{V} \right) \sigma^2_R \tag{14}$$

STEP 4

Different tree splits created with leaf node r_{jt} for pr_{it} on r_{it} , and the best split selected with low weighted average variance.

For $j=1 \dots j_t$ compute $\underset{\gamma}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{x_i \in R_{ij}} l(Y_i, F_{t-1}(x_i) + \gamma)$

Where γ controls the leaf score for minimizing the error between actual data and predicted data for accurate prediction.

$$F_t(x) = Y^{t-1} + pr_{it} \sum_{j=1}^{j_t} \gamma_{jt} I(x \in R_{jt}) \tag{15}$$

For prediction in each iteration, the previous model is updated with the current tree model by the proportion of the contribution rate. This process is repeated continuously until the strong weak learner produces accurate predictions and increases the training score. Similarly, this model was implemented on different buckets, and the final result was merged.

Fig 1. Proposed Architecture for Regression Tree-based Ensemble Method.

2.2.4.2. Testing Phase. Proposed architecture for testing phase is presented in Figure 1. In this phase, 20% unknown data is fed to train model for assessing accuracy and fitness of model. Procedure for prediction of testing data explained in Algorithm 1. Set of residuals ($r_{1to20_1..n}$ for n weak learners for each bucket) generated by each weak learner for each bucket (Figure 2). For choice of window size of future prediction, model evaluated on different chunks of history data and opted with higher accuracy. Eventually, Window size of the past 120 records (600 milliseconds) considered for future predictions with lowest model error. Performance of model with different window size is shown in Figure 3.

In future prediction process, first, all data is checked to which bucket it falls. For the first bucket (i.e., 1 to 20) prediction, sum up the average of each residual and divide by the sum of the lengths of residuals generated by each weak learner during the training phase. Eventually, this is added to each data from the bucket and holds the result in Datalist_1to20. Then the average of each list is multiplied by the fraction of the total data in the bucket. This mechanism controls the contribution of each bucket in the final prediction. The bucket with more values will have a greater contribution to the final prediction. This implies that future predicted value should around from values of this bucket. This process is repeated for each bucket individually, and finally, the results from each bucket sum up to produce the final prediction.

```

Algorithm 1 : Testing Algorithm
INPUT:  $r_{1to20\_1..n}, r_{21to40\_1..n}, r_{41to60\_1..n},$ 
 $r_{61to80\_1..n}, r_{81to100\_1..n},$  main_data, test data
OUTPUT: future prediction
end = test_data.index
windowSize=120
start = end- windowSize
history_data=main_data[start:end]
foreach val in history_data do
  If val <= 20 then
    1to20_data=1to20_data + 1
    resid_sum= $\sum_{i=1}^n avg(r_{1to20\_i})/n$ 
    resid_length= $\sum_{i=1}^n len(r_{1to20\_i})$ 
    prediction =val+(resid_sum/ resid_length)
    Datalist_1to20.append(prediction)
  end if
end for
If 1to20_data! = 0 then
  pred_1to20=(1to20_data/windowSize - 1)*avg(Datalist_1to20)
end if
prediction= pred_1to20+ pred_21to40+ pred_41to60+ pred_61to80+ pred_81to100
return prediction
    
```

2.2.5. Experimental Setup

This section covers the environment setup to implement the various baseline and approached methods for analyzing the fitness of the compared models. To evaluate the strength of the suggested model, a sequence of experiments was performed using the underlying Bitbrain cloud workload dataset, which incorporates genuine traces of virtual machine (VM) metrics. The targeted dataset holds nonlinear and noisy workload behavior, usually in dynamic and heterogeneous cloud environments. Ahead of model training, the dataset was pre-processed using various statistical techniques to ensure data quality and consistency, which helps to enhance model performance and reduce model complexity. All experiments were implemented on a system environment configured with an Intel Core i7 processor (3.6 GHz), 16 GB RAM, 500 GB HDD, and Python 3.10 using various machine learning libraries

2.2.6. Performance Metrics

To estimate the accuracy, effectiveness, and robustness of the model, various performance metrics were evaluated. This ensures that the model’s results are unbiased and generalizable to unseen data. Evaluation metrics were performed for assessing the fitness or accuracy of the model. For the regression problem, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE),

Fig 3. Model Performance with Different Window Size

and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) show how the model’s predictions deviate from the actual data.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\sum (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{n} \right]}$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |Y_i - \hat{Y}_i|$$

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|Y_i - \hat{Y}_i|}{Y_i}$$

Where Y_i be the CPU utilization and, \hat{Y}_i be the estimated CPU utilization and n the number observations in model.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Experimental Results

The suggested method and various baseline models were evaluated on selected performance metrics of the Gwa-Bitbrains dataset for measuring the performance of the models. To ensure the strength and fitness of the approached models, the suggested method was fitted on 80% of the data for training and 20% of the data for testing and validating the model. The proposed model was trained on 138,325 milliseconds of CPU usage data from 116 VMs, and the remaining five VMs’ CPU usage of 34,575 milliseconds was used to validate the model. The resulting models were evaluated through various aforementioned performance metrics to assess their superiority.

3.2 Training Model Performance

As shown in Table 1, all models were trained on the training dataset and measured performance metrics RMSE and MAE to assess the fitness of the models. The proposed method proved its strength with the lowest errors and highest accuracy compared to traditional methods. Hence, the approached method well understands the underlying patterns and can generalize for precise cloud workload prediction. The XGBOOST method shows 77%, 73%, 65%, 63%, and 57% reductions in RMSE errors compared

Table 1. Estimation Errors for Proposed and Baseline Methods (Training)

Models	RMSE	MAE
SARIMA	10.84	6.16
SVM	9.23	4.16
DT	7.08	5.32
RF	6.71	5.28
GB	5.71	3.74
XGBOOST	2.46	1.62
PROPOSED	1.72	1.59

to SARIMA, SVM, DT, RF, and GB methods. The XGBOOST method, with multiple weak learners and regularization, improved model performance. Whereas the suggested technique outperformed and showed a significant reduction of 84%, 81%, 76%, 74%, 70%, and 30% in RMSE compared to all baseline methods, respectively. Similarly, the proposed method enhanced the model accuracy with the lowest MAE.

Fig 4. XGBOOST and Proposed Method trained on Weak Learners for Five VMs CPU usage Estimation (Training)

To evaluate the potential of XGBOOST on nonlinear patterns, a model was trained on 150 regression trees and progressively boosted the performance by shrinking the errors, reaching the 80th iteration. The gently improving performance indicates that the model learns very slowly, which is caused by the learning rate. A too-low learning rate leads to slow model training and higher costs, while a high learning rate causes failure to converge. In the proposed method, the contribution rate, as a substitute for the learning rate, contributes to the model’s progress by following the amount of residuals or errors monitored between actual and estimated CPU usage. Consequently, the model will converge early and accurately. Figure 4 shows that the proposed method hits the minimal error at the 20th iteration, which demonstrates that the model learns accurately and very quickly.

Table 2. Model Error for Proposed and Baseline Methods (Testing)

Models	RMSE	MAE .3
SARIMA	23.11	13.57
SVM	22.05	12.42
RF	11.79	8.13
DT	14.65	9.54
GB	11.12	6.48
XGBOOST	10.27	6.52
Baig SUR ⁽¹¹⁾	9.13	2.57
Al-Asaly MS ⁽²¹⁾ 5min, 15min, 30min, 60min	9.57,9.58, 9.53,9.51	NA
Shahbazinia A ⁽²²⁾	11.94	7.80
Radhika S ⁽²³⁾	21359.49	117.47
Shaikh R ⁽²⁴⁾	9.94	4.02
PROPOSED	8.59	4.47

3.3 Testing Model Performance

Table 2 shows the evaluation results, i.e., estimation errors RMSE and MAE, to recognize the top prediction method for CPU usage estimation for five VMs on selected features of the test dataset. Baseline methods SARIMA, SVM, and DT yield higher errors than all other models, as the single model failed to forecast the future pattern. Ensemble methods RF, GB, and XGBOOST show higher accuracy and approximately minimize the errors by 49%, 37%, and 52% compared to the SARIMA and SVM models. The proposed method outperforms all baseline methods with minimum RMSE and MAE. The proposed methods observed 62%, 61%, 27%, 41%, 22%, and 16% less estimation RMSE than baseline methods, respectively, which reveals higher reductions in errors, showing accurate CPU usage predictions. SARIMA model failed due to assumptions of a fixed seasonal pattern while cloud workload exhibits dynamic, nonlinear behavior. The SVM model shows its weakness due to kernel sensitivity and scalability limitations. RF failed to detect complex behavior due to the restriction of error-aware boosting. Moreover, GB faced issues with highly nonlinear patterns due to a lack of regularization.

In addition, to ensure the model’s strength, reliability, and result validity, a comparative analysis was performed by matching the experimental results with the author’s model outcomes shown in TABLE 2⁽¹¹⁾. They also used the single model approach for GWA-BITBRAIN cloud datacenter resources (CPU) utilization estimation to assess the model’s performance and reliability. The suggested method reduces the model prediction error (RMSE) by approximately 6% when compared to the author’s approach. This lower model error indicates that the suggested method handles large errors wisely by accurately following the nonlinear estimation behavior and minimizing sensitivity to very high workload fluctuations. In contrast, the compared approach struggles to manage large errors as it fails to effectively learn the underlying prediction behavior.

The suggested method reported a higher MAE than the competing model, indicating that the model makes small errors consistently. In cloud infrastructure, small errors that result in little under- or over-allocation do not highly impact performance because they are managed by an elastic provisioning scheme. However, large errors can lead to SLA violations and breach QoS due to extreme under-allocation or over-allocation of resources. These effective results indicate that the suggested method proved its efficiency and accuracy in precise workload prediction on unseen data.

For robustness and generalization, our suggested model’s outcome compared as shown in Table 2⁽²¹⁾. They first use 20 VMs to predict the future workload for one of the VM in one testing day at the interval of 5 min, 15 min, 30 min, and 60 min. The experimental results noted the RMSE of 9.57, 9.58, 9.53, and 9.51 consecutively that is marginally higher than our approached model. Our method observed the reduction of 10.24%, 10.33%, 9.86%, and 9.67% in model prediction error consecutively. This reduction in error indicates the model’s ability to effectively learn the nonlinear behavior in bursty cloud workload and confirmed its strength and superiority.

As stated in Table 2, the suggested method demonstrated lower model error than author’s approach and exhibit its accuracy when compared results with⁽²²⁾. The suggested method reduced the prediction error RMSE by 28.05% and MAE by 42.69% than authors approach. The experimental results points that suggested model handles large fluctuations and small fluctuations very well in prediction of VMs performance degradation. This significant improvement in model accuracy ensures the model capability to effectively identify the temporal behavior in workload for accurate estimation.

Our suggested method determined the performance stability and prediction capability for nonlinear cloud workload dataset when experimental results are compared with ⁽²³⁾. The author implemented the hybrid model with combination of deep learning method GRU and LSTM for cpu resource estimation on cloud workload. The empirical findings observed RMSE and MAE of 21359.49 and 117.47 that is significantly higher than our method as shown in Table 2. The model holding the higher prediction error reveals the failure of model fitness on unseen data. However, our experimental results reported very low RMSE and MAE ensure the model prediction capability with test data.

Moreover, cpu resources estimation on cloud workload GWA-Bitbrain by various machine learning algorithms conducted by ⁽²⁴⁾. In comparison with Decision Tree Regression (DTR) experimental outcome, our proposed approached achieved model error RMSE of 8.59 observed minimal than authors 9.94. This indicates 13.58% reduction in residuals gap of model prediction demonstrates the capability of the proposed model to effectively capture the nonlinear and bursty characteristics of cloud workloads, thereby confirming its robustness, generalization ability, and superior predictive performance.

These significant results carried out by the testing method are ultimately the base provided by the training model. A well-trained model creates a reliable and powerful testing model that effectively extends the observed pattern and maintains stable performance on test data. In the training phase, the newly introduced hyperparameter contribution rate helps to converge and learn quickly by confirming that each weak learner minimizes the appropriate proportion of residual errors in each iteration, compared to the learning rate, which provides a fixed amount of contribution to each weak learner. This fast convergence guides the model to catch residual errors early and truly makes the model capable of accurately identifying complex nonlinear patterns.

Moreover, the single testing model is designed by performing statistical operations on the training model's residuals and the window size depicted in TESTING ALGORITHM 1. The training model's residuals help to identify the prediction behavior quickly, and the statistical operation on the optimized window size contributes to the most occurring value for the future possible expected value.

Proposed method replaced the fixed learning rate of the XGBOOST model with a contribution rate and proved its strength with a 16% higher accuracy in estimation. As shown in Figure 5, the XGBOOST model was implemented with 150 weak learners (estimators), and RMSE was measured from each weak learner individually. However, weak learners gradually decreased error and showed the lowest error at the 80th iteration, after which the error increased for short intervals and then remained constant during prediction. The proposed method, designed as a single strong model from all trained regression trees, improves performance by exceptionally reducing the error.

The approach method outperforms baseline and authors approach by achieving the following strength:

- **Captures cloud workload nonlinear behavior**

Fluctuating demand in cloud resources leads to sudden rises and drops in CPU workload usage. Virtual machine migration, scheduling policies, heterogeneous resources, and network congestion introduce noise into CPU utilization data. This noise generates irregular and unpredictable spikes that deviate significantly from regular workload patterns, thereby contributing to high variability in cloud usage. The proposed hyperparameter contribution rate in the ensemble technique effectively shrinks large prediction errors by dynamically adjusting the gap between actual and predicted values, enabling the model to accurately capture precise workload variations and the underlying non-linear behaviour of cloud workloads. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method accurately captures the upward, downward, and mixed trends present in the dataset. This performance is achieved through the introduced hyperparameter, which enables the training model to effectively learn workload trends and estimate future prediction behaviour on unseen data. During testing, the model leverages an optimal window size combined with statistical operations to estimate accurate predictions by emphasizing the most frequently occurring values.

- **Faster convergence through hyperparameter contribution rate**

The implemented hyperparameter contribution rate effectively regulates the contribution of each regression tree during successive boosting iterations. The proposed technique enables early achievement of accurate predictions by dynamically adjusting the influence of each weak learner based on the proportion of residual error associated with each data point at every iteration. This results in faster convergence while requiring a smaller number of weak learners as illustrated in Figure 4 and Figure 5. In contrast, the learning-rate hyperparameter in the XGBoost ensemble boosting technique can cause the model to converge very slowly when assigned a fixed and small value, as the limited contribution of each boosting iteration may be inadequate to effectively reduce large, highly fluctuating prediction errors driven by non-linear workload residuals.

- **Accurate predictions on unseen data**

The residual-based prediction behaviour learned during training enables the testing model to capture underlying trends in unseen datasets. Furthermore, statistical operations performed on the trained model's residuals, combined with an

Fig 5. Weak Learners Employed in CPU usage Prediction for Five VMs by XGBOOST and Proposed Method (Testing)

appropriate window size, support accurate predictions by emphasizing the most frequently occurring values, as illustrated in Figure 7.

Fig 6. CPU usage prediction for Baseline Vs Proposed (Testing)

Figure 6 shows CPU usage prediction and requirements of CPU capacity in percentage collectively for five VMs for the next 34,575 milliseconds for all models. From the resulting models, the proposed method's estimation is close to actual CPU usage with low model error. This improvement shows that the suggested method's training model, with contribution rate, and testing model helps achieve more accurate predictions than the XGBoost model.

However, Model falls short during the testing prediction in the following scenario

Overfitting: Model fits on training data very accurately and exhibits the good level of performance with minimal prediction error RMSE of 1.72 and MAE of 1.59 including noise and nonlinear, but model slightly found short to generalize on test data and reported the high model error RMSE 8.59 and MAE of 4.47.

Model Complexity: Training the model with new hyperparameter contribution rate in place of learning rate misguide the model to memorize the training behaviour rather than general trend in expectation of high accuracy and converge quickly.

Data Distribution Shift: Training data may hold the patterns or behaviour not present in test data.

The suggested regression tree based ensemble method designed for improving the resource estimation by sequentially minimizing the model error on nonlinear cloud workload dataset. The presented method customized with new hyperparameter contribution rate in place of learning rate to learn and converge quickly. However, The model remains simple with the unnecessary involvement of multiple trend specific machine learning models for capturing the different behaviour separately in expectation of obtaining the high accuracy. This simplicity of model determines clear mathematical structure, easy interpretation, and faster training. Keeping the model simple with customization guides the model to observe the underlying behaviour truly and early in dataset, thereby the proposed model effectively balances the trade-off between simplicity and predictive accuracy.

Fig 7. CPU usage prediction for XGBoost Vs Proposed Methods for Five VMs (Testing)

The proposed method proved its strength in identifying the inherent nonlinear pattern, leading to more accurate predictions. The suggested technique follows the actual data more closely than the XGBoost method, as shown in Figure 7.

4 Conclusion

Handling regression problems with nonlinear continuous time series data prediction is a promising task as patterns reflect behavior unpredictably. In order to achieve accurate estimation, many single model-based techniques are very expensive and

fail to identify the nonlinear behavior. Hybrid models have also increased design complexity, issues of hyperparameter tuning, and interpretability. Consequently, favoring ensemble methods based on bagging and boosting has the potential for multiple models for resource estimation.

Ensemble techniques sequentially reduce the errors and improve the accuracy of the model, but the hyperparameter learning rate causes the model to learn and converge slowly with a huge dataset. In this work, the training and testing model is designed separately to capture the complex nonlinear relationships and achieve accurate predictions on unseen data in the GWA-Bitbrain cloud workload.

The novelty of this work is that the proposed training method emphasizes early error correction achieved by incorporating a contribution rate that replaces the learning rate, determining that each weak learner minimizes the appropriate proportion of residual errors in each iteration. This significantly guides the model to learn the underlying nonlinear patterns and creates a reliable testing model. Furthermore, the single testing method created with statistical operations on the training model's residuals and optimized window size contributes more occurring values to the possible future expected value. To validate and generalize the model's performance, a comparative analysis is performed, where the suggested method achieved higher accuracy with 62%, 61%, 27%, 41%, 22%, and 16% reductions in model error RMSE compared to baseline methods. This method also reduced the prediction error RMSE by 6% and gained a higher MAE than the competitive author's approach.

Based on these findings, it's recommended that a highly fluctuating cloud workload estimation system should prefer the rapid convergence-based boosting ensemble method. This model should evaluate the RMSE for dynamic resource allocation, where occasional high spikes are critical to avoid SLA violations and QoS-based environments, while the higher MAE shows smaller under- or over-allocation, which is absorbed by auto-scaling and does not impact the cloud environment. This effective outcome resulted in a cost-effective environment and efficient utilization of cloud resources.

We conclude that the proposed method effectively helped in gaining an accurate and precise resource estimation for cloud datacenter workload. Our future work will focus on other hyperparameters, methods of tree building, and adaptive window sizes for accurate resource estimation.

5 Acknowledgments

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

In the Department of Computer Science, Rohit Prajapati is a Research Scholar and Dr. Hiren Joshi serves as Professor.

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